

THE NEED OF INTERPRETATION IN MASS MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Annotation: *The subject of research in this article is the mass media discourse. The purpose of the work is to theoretically interpret the mass media discourse in the context of modern society and practice of media communications. The study of mass media discourse considers the features of the platforms, its production and importance, as well as its representation. The work uses a set of methods: comparative analysis and interpretative analysis. The definition of the mass media discourse allows us to expand the understanding of this category in modern media communications.*

Keywords: *interpretation, mass media, media language, media translation.*

In the context of rapid development of technology, different methods of communication, and the increasing role of information in social life, the types of information in different types of media are of particular importance. Now they are seriously competing with receiving and producing other forms of information that are emerging thanks to new technologies. Verbal communication is the key to the progress of human society. Today, we are primarily interested in information provided by the media. Our life is unthinkable without information from the mass media. With the modern development of communication technology, the people of Uzbekistan offer a wide variety of TV news programs in different languages. Also, the Uzbek mass media uses information for media in her trilingual language: Uzbek, Russian and English.

Modern society attempts to locate itself within the republic's and the world's sociopolitical life. As a result, television news is the primary source of public information for the country's audience. The desire for information is one of the primary functions of any person at any time in order to comprehend the world. At the moment, the media has a huge influence on society, consciousness, and people's perceptions. The internal structure of the „media language" concept is based on the consideration of linguostylistic and media features of concrete mass information sublanguages.¹

¹ Dobrosklonskaya T. Medialingvistika: sistemnyj podhod k izucheniyu yazyka SMI [Media Linguistics: Systematic Approach to Language Studying]. — Moscow: Flinta, 2008.

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The internal structure of the „media language" concept is based on the consideration of linguostylistic and media features of concrete mass information sublanguages. Informational and news texts are main constituents of the media speech, which made it possible to transit studying of this area to new quality level — media translation which creates a systematic comprehensive approach to the translation of media language discourse. The most important aspect of television informational and news texts is an objective form of information that reflects a desire for neutrality and depersonification. It is explained by the lack of authorship of news texts, as well as the collaborative way of creation extended on behalf of a group of people: editions, TV companies, and news agencies. The primary function of news text is to inform the audience about socially significant incidents, events, and facts occurring in the country and abroad, as well as to report on various phenomena and their descriptions.

Cliché connections make up 20-30% of the total word count on average. In fact, news texts are very predictable with respect to their use of media text language. Another distinguishing feature of news texts is the use of culture-specific elements to denote objects or phenomena that are characteristic of that culture. The structure of news texts is carefully developed and highly organized, which, coupled with certain features at the linguistic level, allow these texts to be viewed as global and cliché texts of mass information.¹ A newspaper format, understood as a combination of specific external symbols with consistent content and stylistic characteristics, includes external symbols such as page numbers, thematic headlines, illustrations, placement of specific materials and etc.

News texts are characterized by being structured according to the inverted pyramid principle. That is, the most important information is written in the first and above sentences, headings and subheadings. After that, the level of beneficial saturation is reduced. In addition, the format composition of the news material is written on the principle of maximizing the convenience of the reader ("easy to read"). Most of the news are also presented in a concise and complete format so that the reader can select the most interesting news. The first page contains an overview of the most

¹ Silverblatt A. Media Literacy: Keys to Interpreting Media Messages. — London: Praeger, 2001

important reports. News is delivered according to major thematic headlines (world news, sports news, economy, etc.). The message text should be 200-500 words in length. The electronic message text does not span his two screens and provides hyperlinks to relevant material. Culture-specific topics play an important role in the overall information because they implement categories of cultural specificity that are very important for the cognitive aspects of learning news texts. Thanks to the high fidelity, each media theme is distinguished by the presence of a special syntagmatic filling. This thematic hierarchy of linguistic units is of great interest, especially from a practical point of view. The greatest difficulty is translating emotional colors that require changes in vocabulary. Language is full of words that have emotional meanings and implications in addition to logical meanings.

The term "mass media language" refers to all of the texts created and delivered by the media. The stable inner language system characterized by specific linguastylistic features is mass media language.

Mass media language is regarded as a distinct sign system of combined character, with a distinct correlation of verbal and audio-visual components unique to the press, radio, television, and the Internet.

The basic unit of Mass media language is the media text, which is a complex multilevel system based on such main categories as media, mass, integrity, and openness.

The volume and multilevel structure of media text is the verbal speech creation made by mass media. TV information news coverage is organized as follows: Spiegel (short newscast), major domestic events, major international events, sports news, and weather forecast.¹

Special features of national television information news coverage in English include: the prioritization of important official national news; the presentation of international news in a very brief format; and the use of analysts to discuss pressing issues.

Modeling process of translation is connected with the applied tasks and plays the main role in achieving adequate translation. The modeling translation of TV news information texts includes several interconnected aspects: cognitive, linguistic, translation, and journalistic.² According to the developed complex model of TV news information text translation, the translation description is linked not only with the system of equivalency between two languages, but also with the specification of system realization in the translation process. The cognitive aspect includes channel

¹ McLuhan M. *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*. — New York: McGraw-Hill, 1964.

² Мухаметкалиева, С. С. *Media discourse: necessity of studying of media translation*.

broadcasting policy, background knowledge, and TV news information text strategy. Linguistic aspects include genre-stylistic differences and methods of studying TV news information texts.

Translation models, translation strategies, and translation techniques are all part of the translation aspect. The journalistic aspect includes knowledge of the structure of TV news information texts, terminology, and synchronization techniques [4]. News or media text is currently one of the most pressing issues in both social linguistics and translation studies. Media or news text is currently one of the most pressing issues in both social linguistics and translation studies. As media text becomes more prevalent and plays a larger role in people's lives, it should be carefully considered and studied. "Medialinguistics united a wide range of studies related to this dynamic, growing field, as the language of the media," writes Norman Fairclough in his book *Media Discourse*.¹

Despite their apparent simplicity, media translation problems pose a significant challenge for studying. As practice shows, they cannot be overcome solely through the acquisition of "suitable" language forms, nor without an understanding of the logic of their application in a communication language culture. Most communicants speaking a foreign language estimate these forms from positions and do not use them correctly in terms of their native language culture. As a general rule, a key to understanding foreign culture logic is not even a very detailed description of communicative behavior of foreign culture representatives, which is often subjective and usually stereotypic and ethnocentric as they are comments of an interpreter and carrier of another culture, because this logic is defined by a much larger number of factors.

According to the content problems of communicative competence and the methods of its formation in the cognitive fund of a foreign language, which are widely discussed today in language didactics, these facts show the special importance of pragmatic, linguistic, interactive and contextual competence. Knowledge means of communication. Therefore, it is not enough to develop the ability to adequately use a foreign language only by developing general cultural background knowledge (regional geography, learning culture-specific objects, etc.), even if it is very interesting and important. In discourse - this requires the development of a particularly important communicative layer of knowledge (understanding of the interaction of social and pragmatic factors of communication, the nature of speech activity and speech event, cooperation principles and culturally important parameters, and traditional language strategy to achieve communicative goals) in and native and foreign language cultures.

¹ Fairclough N. *Media Discourse*. — London: Hodder Arnold, 1995.

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